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Impact of sewage water on behavioral response and oxygen consumption of fish *Clarius batrachus*

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India permits the untreated flow of residential sewage from most major cities into the country's rivers. The large amount of toxic and harmful chemicals are also mixed along with this, which carry harmful effects on the living things present in it, due to depletion of oxygen and change the physicochemical characteristics of water. In the present study we would like to find out the physicochemical characteristics of water (pH, Temp, DO, BOD, COD, Sulphate, and Sulphite) and behavioral response of the fish due to lack of oxygen. We exposed the fish in the sewage water and observed the behavior of the fish in some time interval (24h, 48h, 72h, 96h, and 120 h, 144h and 168 h). During the study we have find out erratic, fast and drastic movement of the organisms, decreased rate of the opercular movement, increased surfacing and inability with increasing exposure time

1. Introduction

Water is the greatest blessing God has given to mankind; it is necessary for life and is responsible for many bodily functions. Unfortunately, unchecked urbanisation and industrialisation have turned rivers into garbage cans. It is common practise to allow untreated garbage, sewage, and industrial waste to be dumped directly into rivers, which has a negative impact on water quality. Certain businesses' by products are particularly toxic to aquatic life, leading to fish population declines due to unfavourable shifts in the fresh water's physical, chemical, and biological characteristics. The dangers of water contamination have been greatly exacerbated by the combination of industrial and home wastes with a huge number of agricultural herbicides and insecticides.

In addition to lowering the amount of plankton and other food sources for fish, pollution has an effect that spreads for kilometres around the point of discharge. Aside from industrial pollution, domestic sewage from an immense population is dumped into the river, creating undesirable impacts to fish fauna. This significantly decreases the plankton and other organisms, leading to the near extinction of several fish species.

Although while only a small number of Indian cities have facilities for even primary or partial treatment of domestic sewage, the majority of these cities allow their sewage to be released directly into rivers without any sort of treatment. As a result, river water in the surrounding areas has become highly contaminated, and even large towns have facilities for only partial or primary treatment. Sulfates, nitrates, and chlorides are substances that encourage the growth of algae, leading to water blooms that deplete oxygen levels in the water and have hazardous effects if they are released into rivers untreated sewage and laundry detergent from households. An oxygen deficiency due to the raw sewage promotes the collapse of aquatic habitats. Decomposers and detritus feeders thrive on the organic waste found in sewage, which they use for food. as a result, the water's oxygen levels drop even lower,

making it unfit for living organisms like fish. The foul stench of numerous waste materials causes the water to take on the same quality.

Among aquatic organisms, fish are the most vulnerable to the effects of pollution. Presence of environmental stressors, reduce the ability of fish to function normally, both physiologically and behaviorally [1]. Harmful chemicals damage the gills' mucous membrane, which in turn disrupts breathing. And mechanically damage the soft parts sewage and slit bring an earlier aging of the lakes and ponds.

The aerobic digestion of organic and putrescible matter is measured by the biological oxygen demand test, which also quantifies the amount of oxygen needed to sustain the growth and activity of the biological organisms responsible for this process. Moreover, the degree of contamination can be determined with the use of this test. The BOD is a key indicator of the extent to which oxidizable organic matter and oxygen are contributing to water pollution. compounds like sulphides and iron ions [2].

The organism's behaviour is a key mediator between itself and its surroundings [3]. This phenomenon is both a consequence and a cause of toxicological processes at the molecular, physiological, and ecological levels. An organism's ability to navigate its environment, find food, and reproduce can all be inferred from its behavioural reactions (Little, 2002). Population stability may be affected by changes in any of these behaviours, in addition to physiological changes.

Fish normal behaviour is affected by a wide variety of physiological and environmental conditions. Sensory data is usually incorporated centrally once relevant environmental stimuli have been perceived. Behavioral reactions to stimuli are determined by a combination of cerebral and peripheral physiologic changes. Subsequent physiological processes and

external inputs may be influenced by the first shift in behaviour.

Behavioral indicators of toxicity seem appropriate for evaluating the effects of aquatic contaminants on fish populations since behaviour connects physiological function with ecological

2. Material methods

Collect the fish sample from local fish markets and acclimatized in laboratory condition for 10 days and fed with fish palate Collect the sample from sample site of Durg city where the household and domestic water is mixed. After the collection analyzed its physico chemical characteristics and exposed the fish directly in this sewage water and observed the behavior after every 24 hours of the exposure for 1 week time period and along this also observed OD and BOD of the sewage water by APHA AAWAA method presented in Table 1 and 2.

TABLE -1 Physicochemical characteristics of sewage water left the pH all value in mg /l

SN	Parameter	Result
1	pH	7.9
2	Acidity	30.98
3	Alkalinity	73.46
4	Hardness	329.2
5	Ca	316
6	Mg	13.2
7	DO	2.8
8	COD	188.8
9	BOD	2.87

TABLE -2 BOD of the sewage water

S.N	Time of exposure	BOD
1	24	3.15
2	48	3.49
3	72	3.55
4	96	3.66
5	120	3.82
6	144	3.92
7	168	4.12

processes. The presence of these pollutants causes varying degrees of impacts on fish depending on the species, sex, age, size, general physical condition, exposure time, concentration of pollutants, kind of toxicant employed, and environmental [4-5]. Water properties including hardness, alkalinity, and hydrogen ion concentration may affect these consequences [6].

3. Results and Discussion

Behavioral changes in *Clarius batrachus* in response to exposure to sewage water are depicted in Table 3.

TABLE - 3 Behavioral changes in *Clarius batrachus* in response to exposure to sewage water

Hours	Behavioral changes after exposure		
24	No obvious change. Normal behavior.		
48	No obvious change. Normal behavior.	Heavy mucous secretion. Rapid opercular and mouth movement.	Heavy mucous secretion, Surfacing. Fast, erratic, darting swimming movement.
72	Heavy mucous secretion. Rapid opercular and mouth movement.		
96	Heavy mucous secretion. Surfacing.		
120	Fast, erratic, darting swimming movement.		
144			
168			

After exposure in sewage water it was observed that with the duration of exposure fishes showed rapid opercular and mouth movements. Increased surfacing accompanied by rapid, erratic, and slashing strokes. There was

excessive mucus production for at least 48 hours. Fishes exposed to a poisonous medium for 96 hours exhibited irregular swimming, jerky motions, respiratory discomfort, and a drive to flee. At 120 and 168 hours, it's clear that mucus secretion has grown dramatically. On the other hand, the animal acted erratically, racing into the tank wall without caring that it might get hurt. The fishes' erect posture, with their bodies resting on their caudal fins, was a sign of dizziness. Instead of the usual surfacing behaviour, erratic lateral motions were seen. The fast beating of the operculum suggested difficulty breathing. There was a thick layer of mucous discharge all over it for protection.

Literature review reveals that fish exposed to a variety of toxicants exhibit a wide range of abnormal behaviours, such as increased opercular activity at first, followed by a gradual decrease with time [7], surface breathing, swimming, shoaling disruption, and increased vulnerability to predators [8]. If breathing rapidly is an option, it could help you avoid coming into touch with a poisonous substance. The current author agrees with Katja et al., 2005 that the increased surfacing phenomenon seen in the case of fishes exposed to low concentration of effluent can be related to a higher oxygen demand throughout the exposure time [9].

One of the most useful indicators of both energy expenditure and overall metabolism, an animal's respiratory potential or oxygen consumption is a crucial physiological parameter for gauging the effects of toxic stress [10]. Breathing problems are more common when hazardous substances are present. Acute pesticide poisoning often manifests first as difficulty breathing, as noted by Holden (1973) [11]. The information gained from this is not only helpful in determining the animal's sensitivity or resistance, but can also be used to draw conclusions about the animal's behaviour. According to the author of this piece, an increase in the breathing rate of fish in a hypoxic environment is due to the fish's inability to efficiently take in oxygen. Toxic stress, brought on by the increased uptake of toxicants from the waste water, may be reducing bottom-dwelling activity. *Mystus kellicottii* and *Gasterosteus aculeatus* have both been documented to exhibit toxicant-induced behaviours

similar to what has been observed in humans [12-13]. Workers have noticed that fish of several kinds exhibit strange behaviour after being exposed to pollution. Fish suffer damage to their peripheral organs and a decrease in swimming activity after consuming pollutant-contaminated phytoplanktons and zooplankton as food [14]. In *Tilapia mossambica*, cadmium exposure results in frequent surfacing, uneven opercular motions, and loss of balance [15]. When exposed to Gammalin 20, Gramazone, Primextra, and Sandox, fingerlings of *Oreochromis niloticus* and *Sarotherodon galilaeus* swam erratically, as described by Fafioye (1990) [16]. Adeogun (1994) found that *Oreochromis niloticus* and *Clarias gariepinus* exhibited irregular behaviour after being exposed to *Raphia hookeri* extracts, including darting up and down the water column and swimming on both the dorsal and ventral sides [17]. Fish subjected to pesticides like Keltane, Bisulton, Pydrin, Dursban, and Permethrin exhibited altered schooling habits, namely Fathead minnows (*Pimphales promelas*) and Rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) [18]. Overturning periods for *C. gariepinus* and *O. niloticus* treated to aqueous and ethanolic extracts of *Parkia biglobosa* and *Raphia vinifera* decreased with increase in concentration [5]. After being exposed to lead, Brook trout, *Salvelinus fontinalis*, exhibited hyperactivity, irregular swimming, and loss of equilibrium, according to research published by Holcombe et al. (1976) [18]. Also noted as symptoms of mercury poisoning in Rainbow trout, *Salmo gairdneri* are a loss of equilibrium, frequent surfacing and sinking, bursts of irregular swimming, and a gradual development of lethargy [19].

Fish behavioural indicators have been presented by numerous studies as a method for ecologically appropriate monitoring of environmental contamination [20]. Individual fish display normal behaviour in accordance with predetermined physiological sequences activated by neural networks [21]. Premature interruption of such sequences is likely to cause undesirable changes in behaviour. The toxic effects of aquatic contaminants can have devastating impacts on organisms' ability to adapt to their

environments and respond appropriately to physiological stimuli.

Channa striatus exposed to fertiliser wastewater exhibited altered behavioural responses, including increased opercular mobility and decreased bottom dwelling activity [22]. There was a marked decrease in all types of surface activity, including swimming, walking, running, jumping, maintaining balance, and flapping the fins. A slowness in the eyes' movement was noted. There was a significant uptick in the rate of circular motion as the wastewater concentration rose. Fish breathing rates were shown to increase when exposed to hypoxia. According to Patil and David's (2008) research on behaviour and respiratory dysfunction as an index of Malathion toxicity in Labeorohita, while the control fish were active with controlled and coordinated movements, the toxicant exposed fish exhibited irregular, erratic, darting movements and loss of equilibrium due to inhibition of Ache activity, which accumulated acetylcholine in cholinergic synapses and resulted in hyper stimulation [23].

The results are consistent with those of other researchers, including Dube and Hosetti (2010) [24], Rao et al. (2003) [25], and Parma de Croux et al.(2002) [26]. Test fishes exposed to Dimethoate over longer periods of time displayed erratic swimming, increased surfacing, decreased rate of opercular motions, excessive mucus secretion, decreased agility, and an inability to maintain normal posture and balance, according to research by Pandey et al., (2009) [27].

Conclusion

During the study we have find out erratic, fast and drastic movement of the organisms, decreased rate of the opercular movement, increased surfacing and inability with increasing exposure time. Thus, Clarius batrachus having impact on behavioral response and oxygen consumption of sewage water.

Conflict of Interest

Author(s) declared no conflict of interest.

Ethical Compliance Standard

NA.

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